

reactions of DDD and BHC are rendered increasingly more irreversible with increasing amounts of organic solvents and ionic and non-ionic surfactants.

$k_{r,h}^0$ values: A perusal of the values of $k_{r,h}^0$ shows that there is no regularity in the variation of $k_{r,h}^0$ values with the increasing amounts of organic solvents and ionic and non-ionic surfactants. Meites^{5a} also hinted at the limitation of $k_{r,h}^0$ in interpreting the results. However, the influence of increasing amounts of organic solvents and ionic and non-ionic surfactants on the electrode reactions of DDD and BHC can be studied^{1a-1c} in terms of the value of the potential-dependent rate constant ($k_{r,h}$) at a suitable potential which should be such as to lie between the potential corresponding to the foot and the plateau of the polarographic wave. At such a potential both the rate of the electron-transfer and the diffusion determine the magnitude of the current. The values of $k_{r,h}$ at such a potential (for the I step of BHC this potential is -0.40 V while for the II one this is -1.26 V; for the I step of DDD this potential is -0.50 V and for the II step this is -1.30 V vs SCE) have been obtained. From these values it is seen that the parameter $k_{r,h}$ at such a potential decreases with increasing amounts of organic solvents and also with increasing amounts of ionic and non-ionic surfactants. This shows that the irreversible electrode reactions of DDD and BHC are rendered increasingly more irreversible with increasing concentrations of organic solvents and surfactants. A decrease in i_d and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ with increasing amounts of organic solvents and surfactants support this conclusion.

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Application of *ortho*-Lithiation Reaction. Synthesis of some 3-Ethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins

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Manuscript received 8 December 1988, revised 2 May 1989,
accepted 23 May 1989

VARIOUS 3,4-dihydroisocoumarins bearing an alkyl group at C-3 with oxygenation on aromatic ring occur in nature. Literature survey reveals that there are very few reports for the synthesis of such compounds¹⁻³. Hence, an investigation on the synthesis of some 3-ethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins has been carried out using *ortho*-lithiation on carboxamide followed by alkylation with an epoxide^{4,5}.

- 1,2 a; $R_1 = \text{OMe}, R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = \text{H}$
 b; $R_2 = \text{OMe}, R_1 = R_3 = R_4 = \text{H}$
 c; $R_4 = \text{OMe}, R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 d; $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = \text{H}, R_3 = \text{Me}$
 e; $R_2 = \text{Me}, R_1 = R_3 = R_4 = \text{H}$
 f; $R_1 = R_2 = \text{OMe}, R_3 = R_4 = \text{H}$

Substituted-*N*-methylbenzamides (1a-f) were lithiated with *n*-BuLi at room temperature under inert atmosphere and the resultant *ortho*-lithio derivatives were subjected to alkylation with 1,2-butylene oxide. Alkaline hydrolysis and usual work up⁶ afforded 3-ethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins (2a-f) which were characterised by analytical, ir and pmr spectral data (Table 1).

Experimental

Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer. Solid compounds were crystallised from ether-hexane.

N-Methylbenzamides (1a-f): *m*-Methoxy-(1a, m.p. 65°), *p*-methoxy-(1b, m.p. 120°), *o*-methoxy-(1c, b.p. 147-48°/2 mm), *m*-methyl-(1d, b.p. 178-80°), *p*-methyl-(1e, m.p. 146°) and 3,4-dimethoxy-(1f, m.p. 127°)-*N*-methylbenzamides were prepared by the action of $\text{SOCl}_2/\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2$ on the corresponding aromatic acids.

Lithiation of N-methylbenzamides (1a-f) and alkylation of ortho-lithioderivatives with 1,2-butylene oxide. General procedure: To a well-stirred solution of *N*-methylbenzamide (1a-f; 5 g) in dry THF (75 ml, freshly distilled over LiAlH_4) was added at room temperature *n*-BuLi (0.128 mol) in

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 3-ETHYL-3,4-DIHYDROISOCOUMARINS (2)*

Compd. no.	Yield %	B.p. (10 mm) °C	Mol. formula	$\nu_{\max}^{**}$ cm^{-1}	δ
2a	22	160	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$	1 715 (δ -lactone)	1.09 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.84 (2H, complex, CH_2CH_2), 2.6 and 3.2 (2H, dd, J 11, 17 Hz and 4, 17 Hz), 3.9 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.38 (1H, complex, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{O})\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 7.1 (1H, dd, J 1, 8 Hz, H_6), 7.3 (1H, t, J 8 Hz, H_7) and 7.7 (1H, dd, J 1, 8 Hz, H_6)
2b	29	72 ^a	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$	1 720 (δ -lactone)	1.06 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.8 (2H, complex, CH_2CH_2), 2.9 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, benzylic CH_2), 3.84 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.4 (1H, complex, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{O})\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 6.8 (2H, complex, H_6 and H_7) and 8.05 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H_6)
2c	13	140	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$	1 730 (δ -lactone)	1.05 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.8 (2H, complex, CH_2CH_2), 2.85 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, benzylic CH_2), 3.9 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.2 (1H, complex, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{O})\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$) and 6.7–7.4 (3H, complex, H_6 , H_6 and H_7)
2d	19	130	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$	1 730 (δ -lactone)	1.08 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.8 (2H, complex, CH_2CH_2), 2.34 (3H, s, aromatic CH_3), 2.85 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, benzylic CH_2), 4.39 (1H, complex, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{O})\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 7.1 (2H, complex ortho-coupled H_6 and H_6 protons signals merged) and 7.75 (1H, s ^b , H_6)
2e	17	155	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$	1 725 (δ -lactone)	1.01 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.8 (2H, complex, CH_2CH_2), 2.35 (3H, s, aromatic CH_3), 2.85 (2H, d, benzylic CH_2), 4.35 (1H, complex, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{O})\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 7.0 (1H, s ^b , H_6), 7.1 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H_7), 7.9 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H_6)
2f	23	74 ^a	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$	1 720 (δ -lactone)	1.1 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.8 (2H, complex, CH_2CH_2), 2.7 and 3.1 (2H, dd, J 11, 17 Hz and 4, 17 Hz), 3.8 and 3.9 (each 3H, s, OCH_3 at C-5 and C-6), 4.3 (1H, complex, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{O})\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 6.9 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H_7) and 7.8 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H_6)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

**Compounds 2a, 2b and 2f taken in nujol and 2c, 2d and 2f neat. ^aM.p. (°C). ^bSignals not resolved into a meta-coupled doublets.

dry ether under N_2 -atmosphere during 10 min. The resulting red metalation mixture was refluxed for 45 min, cooled to 0 to -5° and to it 1,2-butylene oxide (9.0 ml) in dry ether was added during 5 min. The reaction mixture was stirred at 0° for 2 h and further 2 h at room temperature. The alkaline hydrolysis workup^o of the reaction mixture gave the 3-ethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin derivatives. Thus 5-methoxy-, 6-methoxy-, 8-methoxy-, 7-methyl-, 6-methyl- and 5,6-dimethoxy-3-ethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins were synthesised (2a – f, Table 1).

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

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Studies on Flavonoids. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 7-n-Butoxy-6-nitro/H-flavones, -flavonols and -flavanones

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Manuscript received 24 December 1988, revised 3 May 1989, accepted 23 May 1989

FLAVONOIDS have been found to be associated with diverse biological activities¹. The present work reports the preparation of 7-n-butoxy-6-nitro-flavones, -flavonols and -flavanones and 7-n-butoxy-flavones, -flavonols and -flavanones of types 2, 3 and 4 respectively. These are derived from previously synthesised² 2'-hydroxy-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcones and 2'-hydroxy-4'-n-butoxychalcones (1) which have been prepared from 2-hydroxy-4-n-

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